

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

PERCEIVE

Perception and Evaluation of Regional and Cohesion Policies
by Europeans and Identification with the Values of Europe

Perception and Evaluation of Regional and Cohesion policies by Europeans and Identification with the Values of Europe

PERCEIVE

GA nr. 693529

D 7.2 ‘Dissemination and Communication Strategy’

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Short

Medium

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1. Abstract

The aim of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy is to lay down the path for reaching out in the most effective way the targets of PERCEIVE project.

As the Horizon 2020 research program clearly states, the goal is to not only reach out to academics but also to research users and the wider audience, and make it aware that it will greatly benefit from the research findings and activities.

We assume that the expected impact of the research is to make major conceptual, methodological and analytical contribution towards a better understanding of the relationship between European regional policies, local and regional identities and the perception of the added value of the EU by its citizens. Thus, by launching an online campaign, we want to facilitate the understanding and reflection on how different senses of belonging emerge as a consequence of the Cohesion Policy in different European regions.

The following pages will structure the strategy in terms of time, contents and actions: “at what stage which kind of action will be undertaken and directed to who”.

We will illustrate our objectives, how we see PERCEIVE in its brand identity, how do we want to manage the research content, through which channels and along a specific timeline.

Finally, how do we want to keep track of PERCEIVE communication’s impact.

2. Objectives

2.1. Macro objectives

To maximise comprehensibility of the project at different levels we will develop a multi-layer project content structure tailored to meet different approaches to knowledge and understanding of three main targets:

- a. Academics
- b. Practitioners
- c. Citizens

To support a 2-step visibility of research activities we will raise project awareness (first step of contact), reach out for project targets (second step of contact) and make a communication impact by:

- I. fostering interaction with project targets (feedbacks and engagement)
- II. collecting feedback and qualitative information from theme enthusiasts (gamification and engagement)
- III. web positioning of PERCEIVE on Cohesion Policy keywords (SEO)
- IV. enabling easy lookup of PERCEIVE deliverable tools (eg: guidelines)

2.2 Specific objectives

Macro 1 goals breakdown (maximise comprehensibility):

- Analysis on project expected outcomes (hints from focus groups)
- Grant a relevant communication delivery during the project
- Make research temporary findings easily shareable among different professional targets
- Give a visually engaging representation of the research highlights for theme enthusiasts
- Develop ready-to-use guideline tools for EU project practitioners

Macro 2 goals breakdown (support visibility, reach out, engage):

- Build a map of relevant communication hubs and amplifiers
- Open specific communication channels to reach non-academic research users
- Reach out for civil society's theme enthusiasts
- Develop interaction windows to make the research process as open as possible to comments and contributions from the web
- Develop a specific dissemination action plan for temporary findings
- Develop a specific dissemination action plan for EU projects communication guidelines
- Share European project impact communication variables with the EU political architecture (EU

policy makers and practitioners)

- Share European project impact and communication variables with the EU lobbying architecture (policy influencers and advisors)

Macro1. Contents

Partners	Surface Contents	In Depth Contents	Technical Contents	Guidelines (?)
Academic	project abstract, research objectives.	research, methodology and structure, theoretical framework.	temporary findings, open data sets, final papers.	
Professional	professional questions final deliverable aims.	infographics	temporary findings summary.	how to, recommendations and impact insights.
Citizens	questions	project infographics temp findings infographics.	■	

Macro 2. Actions

Partners	Awareness	Comprehension	Engagement	Endorsement
Academic	■	■	■	■
Practitioners	■	■	■	■
Citizens	■	■	■	

3. Targets

3.1 Breakdown

The target is the group of people to whom we want to communicate PERCEIVE. We are going to breakdown our target into three labels: academics, practitioners and citizens, in order to better grasp its complexity and to reach out to everyone more effectively.

3.1.1 Academics

Academics include professors, researchers, PhD students, etc. whose work is research and, possibly, who publish books and papers on journals. They also attend conferences, often travelling around the world. We subdivided this target into: learned societies, research groups and academic conferences.

3.1.1.1 Learned societies

A learned society (also known as a learned academy, scholarly society or academic association) is an organization that exists to promote an academic discipline or profession, or a group of related disciplines or professions. Most learned societies are non-profit organizations, and many are professional associations. Their activities typically include holding regular conferences for the presentation and discussion of new research results and publishing or sponsoring academic journals in their discipline. Some also act as professional bodies, regulating the activities of their members in the public interest or the collective interest of the membership.

Language: academic

Content: academic temporary findings, conference speeches and quotes and other strictly academic materials

Interests: mainly academic prestige, very theoretical even if applied to practice

3.1.1.2 Research groups

Language: academic

Content: dataset, working papers, survey and focus groups' results

Interests: mainly academic prestige, very theoretical even if applied to practice

3.1.1.3 Academic conferences

An academic conference is a conference for researchers (not necessarily academics) to present

and discuss their work. Together with academic or scientific journals, conferences provide an important channel for exchange of information between researchers.

Language: academic

Content: academic temporary findings presented as working papers

Interests: mainly academic prestige, very theoretical even if applied to practice

3.1.2 Practitioners

Practitioners are professionals who work in the EU or for the EU, or the manage projects financed by the EU. We divided this target into: EU political architecture and institutional architecture, Local Managing Authorities, EU Lobbying Architecture, EU projects management professionals and professional working in commercial companies dealing with EU funding programs.

3.1.2.1 EU Political and institutional architecture

It is made up by EU's bodies and relative policy makers, that constitutes the EU structure. This group includes both executive and consultative bodies. The aim of targeting this group is to shape directly the institutional discourse. The language must be more formal and technical, depending on the degree of liase with the EU interest.

- **European Commission:** politically independent executive arm

Language: very formal and institutional

Content: infographics, impact insights, guidelines

Interests: European Union as a whole

- **European Parliament**

Language: formal but advocacy oriented because it addresses citizens concerns

Content: infographics, impact insights, guidelines, interviews

Interests: European citizens

- **Council of the European Union**

Language: formal

Content: infographics, impact insights, guidelines

Interests: European governments

- **European Parliament Committees:** committees bring forth the interests of European citizens and they are classified according to different topics (eg. European Committee of the Regions).

Language: formal but advocacy oriented because it addresses citizens concerns

Content: infographics, impact insights, guidelines, interviews, surveys

Interests: European citizens, according to specific topics

- **European Union Agencies:** they have an operative role and very technical objectives because they implement the Commission's policies (eg. Eurofound).

Language: very technical

Content: infographics, impact insights, guidelines, reports, recommendations

Interests: implementing efficiently EU policies

- **European Union Policies:** these are guidelines of a particular policy, our focus will be on Cohesion Policy of course, so on Regional Policy. EU policies are implemented thanks to different funds.

Language: technical but also shade an advocacy light on the importance of the policies

Content: infographics, impact insights, guidelines, reports

Interests: improve European citizens' well being (social and economic status), achieve positive results/impact

3.1.2.2 Local Managing Authorities

Member states are responsible for managing programmes that are supported by Cohesion Policy. A designated managing authority provides information on the programme, selects projects and monitors implementation. This category includes regions (e.g. Regione Emilia-Romagna) and other authorities such as ministries and departments at national level.

Language: technical, related to Cohesion Policy's implementation

Content: guidelines, reports, infographics, recommendations, impact insights

Interests: manage efficiently EU policies implementation

3.1.2.3 EU lobbying architecture

This category includes policy advising and policy influencing organizations, some of them more advocacy-oriented (explicitly in defence of certain values relevant for the civil society) e.g. Friends of Europe. This category includes delegations as well, which represent, on the other hand, specific interests of a peculiar organization or institution (eg. Confindustria's delegation in Brussels).

- **Think tanks:** have a stronger research orientation

Language: balance between academic (theoretical base), technical (implementation) & advocacy (more emotional), depending on the degree of research/advocacy orientation

Content: academic findings, surveys, guidelines, infographics, interviews, reports

Interests: lobbying in the EU regarding different topics such as 'active citizenship'

- **Nonprofit organizations:** weaker research orientation compared to think tanks

Language: advocacy (emotional, defense of European values eg. democracy, sense of belonging to the EU but also policy shaping-oriented)

Content: guidelines, infographics, interviews, reports, quotes defending the values they endorse, emotional pictures

Interests: lobbying in the EU regarding different topics such as 'active citizenship'

- **Delegations**

Language: technical but also policy shaping-oriented, if the topic concerns their interest as organization or institution

Content: academic temporary findings, guidelines, dossiers, infographics, interviews, reports, quotes in line with their interests

Interests: lobbying in the EU regarding topics that impact directly on them

3.1.2.4 EU project management professionals

This category includes consultancy companies followed and/or paid by professionals, training schools (seminars, masters, etc.) and online platforms. In this case our guidelines on communication may interest European projects' professionals on large scale.

Language: a mix between academic and technical

Content: guidelines, dossiers, infographics, case studies, practical information 'how to'

Interests: increase prestige and professionalism and their community

3.1.2.5 Professionals working in commercial companies dealing with EU funding programs (e.g. competitiveness's funds for enterprises)

We don't plan to reach for specific companies, but rather to reach for individuals with corporate roles.

Language: a mix between technical and citizen oriented

Content: guidelines, dossiers, infographics, case studies, practical information 'how to'

Interests: increase knowledge for corporate brand awareness opportunity or funding opportunities

3.1.3 Citizens

3.1.3.1 Wider themes enthusiasts

This category includes people with an high degree of knowledge and currently updated, interested in in-depth contents, but not EU professionals. They could be much more interested in contents in their own language than in English, because it's easier to discuss.

According to age, we identify two segments with more free time:

25-40 years old - fragmented use of the web, less TV and more English-friendly

55-70 years old - encyclopedic use of the web, more TV and radio & less English friendly

Themes

- EU and foreign policy enthusiasts search for topics on governance and policy-making in Brussels
- Politics and political economy enthusiasts start searching from domestic politics

Interests

- Deepening: interested only in finding accurate information, opinions, findings. They could be readers of a specific magazine (online or offline), a specialised blogger or listener of a particular radio show. In addition, they could surf on the web looking for new interesting projects or platforms.
- Interaction: debates lovers and willing to share their perspective when possible. They could have a participatory spirit with a constructive and open attitude or they could have a negative approach and use the interaction as a sort of personal outburst. Comments to articles and active participation in forum debates are some examples of daily actions.
- Engagement: experience-based people who prefer the simulation and gaming activity

Location

To different locations correspond different degrees of interest:

- Less developed or transitional regions: we expect more discontent about the effectiveness of EU policies, but also more enthusiasm from new state members.
- More developed regions: more awareness about EU funding programs and their impact on local services and livability.

3.1.3.2 Daily general news consumers

This public is interested in being almost daily up-to-date on national and international news, through TV, radio, newspapers and online news. These people usually have a superficial reading through the news, but they seldom have specific drivers different, from the thematic ones, that lead them to deepen some news in particular.

Age, two segments with more free time:

25-40 years old - fragmented use of the web, less TV and more English friendly

55-70 years old - encyclopedic use of the web, more TV and radio and less English friendly

Drivers & Interests

- Objective, data and numbers. These segment is data representation and numbers enthusiast, interested in better understanding society, science or, in general, complicated topics. Graphics, charts, diagrams, infographics, animated charts on paper, broadcasted or online are the kind of representations they like.
- Identification. They are also followers of the news on 'being European' topic, especially because they personally tend to project on their personal experience. Current events in other EU countries, which indirectly raise questions for them, are their major interest. They are looking for answers. They could be pro or cons equality.

Location

To different locations correspond different degrees of interest:

Less developed or transitional regions: we expect more discontent about the effectiveness of EU policies, but also more enthusiasm from new state members.

More developed regions: more awareness about EU funding programs and their impact on local services and livability.

3.1.3.3 Students

This is the narrowest segment, composed by students who have to deepen Cohesion Policy's themes as a school/university duty or for personal reasons, but always connected to some topics recently studied. They fall into the research users' category.

Age, two different study stages:

14-19 years old - high-school students

19-25 years old - University students, especially political economy students, international relations and European studies

To different locations correspond different degrees of interest:

- More developed regions. They have much more interested in datas, findings, evidences. They are more aware of EU Cohesion Policy topics.
- Less developed or transition regions. They are also interested in new opportunities, in a future occupation perspective and in well understanding the nowadays situation and giving their opinions about it, yet they might be skeptical about EU policies benefits.

See attachments A.

4. Identity

4.1 Project branding

4.1.1 Mission, Vision, Values

In order to build an effective communication strategy, through different channels, we need to delineate a brand of PERCEIVE project, i.e. a unique value proposition expressed in a relevant and differentiated way such that it creates preference and loyalty among key targets. PERCEIVE, as a research project, aims at explaining how the European Union invests one third of its budget in Cohesion Policy, how this policy is differently implemented and communicated in members states, and how it does, or does not, contribute to strengthening the European identity and to creating support for the European project. It follows that PERCEIVE, as a brand, has to be clear, transparent, factual, evidence-based and light caster towards taken for granted assumptions. It needs to have an investigative tone.

PERCEIVE's main research added values are 'multidisciplinarity' and 'innovativeness', which, together, aim at 'scientific rigor'. Economic analysis, political science and economic sociology are combined together in the project. In addition, econometric analysis and mathematical modelling are implemented with discourse analysis and social constructivism. PERCEIVE's brand image should communicate the these 'multidisciplinarity' and 'innovativeness' with an open-minded tone in order to take to the surface some underground and submerged relationship between what happens at a regional level, the collective understanding of Europe and its cohesion variables and policies.

4.1.2 From values to brand components

Given the values stated at 4.1.1, we are developing a set of brand components based on the theoretical and strategic assumption that "a brand is a set of expectations" (Seth Godin).

What do we want our targets to expect from PERCEIVE?

As a matter of fact, PERCEIVE addresses the controversial complexity of the identity and development of the European Union. So, PERCEIVE's identity as a research project, as we mentioned in the previous paragraph, is linked to two concepts: 'multidisciplinarity' and 'innovativeness'. The innovativeness is connected to the methodological variety of approaches involved. 'Multidisciplinarity' materializes in the association of two intertwined research processes: the economic analysis of processes of economic convergence among European regions and the analysis of the symbolic and discursive processes connected to the formation of the identity of Europe. Therefore, the brand identity of PERCEIVE should be able grasp the controversial aspect of the research: the communication strategy targets this aspect in paragraph 4.1.5.

4.1.3 From brand components to keywords

Arising from a dichotomic value set, that originates a positive tension between opposite brand components (unity and diversity), a world is generated in which different semantic poles merge into each other, creating a semantic space in which project brand and project communication strategies may shift depending on context, application and tools.

Wordcloud 1.

Within this context we want to pick some priority keywords that will help us define both identity layers and, on a second level, the communication personas we need to develop for a coherent approach to multi-purpose, multi-faceted content dissemination.

Wordcloud 2.

4.1.4 From brand components to visual elements: graphic guidelines

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Graphic Guidelines

Rational

Together and apart at same time

PERCEIVE identity is based on semantic elements that bond together the perception of Europe as a work in progress, as something that has many directions and many counterposed meanings. Union vs strong singularities. Definition vs dispersion. Shifting identities and perception of static bureaucracy.

Shapes & Particles

The basic element of PERCEIVE visual identity is the particle. A unity that is etymologically conceived as 'part' of a bigger system. Particles sum up to shape wider figures, bond together to create new elements, break apart to generate reactions and energy. A coherent metaphore of the cohesion movements within the European Union.

1. Cohesion

Even though the glyph is composed by separated elements it still produces an overall perception of cohesion and meaning. Europe has a strong identity internationally, but so have its nations.

3. Movement

The way the dots are positioned confers movement to the composition (it can be seen in different directions, depending on the way you look at it). Meaning that the relation between the dots is not immanent, but changes through time and perception.

2. Dispersion

The dots are together and apart at same time. Some of the them are very close one another and others very distant. There is no specific rational in how the dots are located, still they compose a coherent figure.

4. Diversity

European regions are all different one another. The dots are different one from another, in color and dimension representing diversity as a positive aspect, even in unity.

Color composition

Difference is visually enhanced by the application of different colors. The color ratio and balance is designed to convey the same color balance of the European Flag. Indigo Blue and Light Blue balance together while yellow light points remind us of the stars of the Union.

Indigo Blue

C: 100 M: 93 Y: 26 K: 12
R: 39 G: 52 B: 114

Light Blue

C: 62 M: 20 Y: 0 K: 0
R: 3 G: 169 B: 44

Amber Yellow

C: 0 M: 25 Y: 100 K: 0
R: 295 G: 193 B: 0

Monocromo

PERCEIVE logo is designed to keep a strong impact in its monocromo version.

It's fundamental to use the B/W version for B/W print in order to avoid less impactful shades of gray. It is also important to use mono-colored versions of the logo on full flat background colors.

Minimums size

In order to get a clear view of the PERCEIVE glyph we recommend not to use it under a 9mm print height (32mm width). If there's a technical need for it we recommend to avoid using the glyph and use only the logotype.

Interactions

In order to get a clear view of PERCEIVE logo has a required minimum distance of 1/4th its width. For instance, on a 6cm application it requires a 1.5cm buffer distance.

Wrong versions

PERCEIVE logo is not meant to be stretched, colored with colors that are not black, white, shades of gray or the brand colors. It is strictly forbidden to write the logotype with a different font and to apply the colored version on full color backgrounds.

Composition

In order to make its usage more flexible, PERCEIVE logo has several possible compositions. Both horizontal and vertical, with or without tagline, with or without logotype, depending on the application needed.

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Institutional Fonts

PERCEIVE brand identity rely on the use of two separate fonts.
Montserrat Black for headlines and straight communication graphics.
Neuzeit Book for body and paragraph composition.

Montserrat

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#\$%^&*()

Neuzeit

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#\$%^&*()

4.1.5 Brand borders and directions

4.1.5.1 What PERCEIVE brand is not

In order to avoid misunderstandings, we want to clarify what PERCEIVE is not, since it might not be taken for granted that most of our targets knows what the project is. We identified four main statements to underline which kind of misconceptions might emerge.

1. **Perceive is not the European Union or a EU propaganda tool.** It must be clear that we don't talk on behalf of the EU: we are EU-funded project, but we do not represent directly this institution.
2. **Perceive is not a political party.** PERCEIVE discuss and research about policies not politics. In this sense, we are a apolitical.
3. **Perceive is not a private company.** We don't represent any economic interests and we are not making any profit out of the project's activities.
4. **Perceive is not an opinion outlet or a debate forum.** This is a delicate statement: chances are that exchange of opinions will take place. Nevertheless, we can foster dialogue only if we relate it to a specific data-based answers.

4.1.5.2 What PERCEIVE doesn't want to communicate

As we explained in the previous paragraph, it is important to carefully manage PERCEIVE's identity. Hence, we selected four main statements that sum up implicit or subtle message that we want to avoid in our communication:

1. **Waste of money on the project.** We don't want people to think that we are using the project's budget inappropriately (pictures of fancy dinners or hotels during meetings).
2. **To be only aimed at academic speculation and have no practical impact at all.** PERCEIVE is not just research, but we want people to be aware of the side impacts and activities related to it.
3. **Shouldn't be an end in itself.** We want Horizon 2020's approach to clearly emerge from our communication of the project. Since Horizon aims at more than purely researching: its goal is to have an impact on creating jobs and reach out to a larger audience than the academia.
4. **Political lobbying.** PERCEIVE doesn't have an advocacy component: we want to inform people on our research activities and positive consequences. However, our work might be useful for those who do political lobbying, with which will interact along the project development.

4.1.5.3 Controversial issues management and limits

We need a solid approach towards topics that might create antagonism or criticism related to PERCEIVE. In order to detangle this task, we have tried to list the main controversial issues that nowadays are related to the EU. Overall, we want to have an informative take and cause-effect reasoning concerning these issues - we don't want to have a clear cut statement. We delineate a sort of 'how to' position PERCEIVE in the dialogue with web users on the topics that might emerge. As a general principle, in addressing controversial issues PERCEIVE is guided by Copenhagen criteria.

1. **BREXIT.** Considering that one of our partner is from the UK, it would be useful to consider how to handle this issue. We would inform first through a valid source (external link), but also underline the importance of investigating the regional level. In doing so, we highlight the importance of PERCEIVE as a counterbalance in respect to centrifugal forces. More specifically PERCEIVE investigates the relationship between euroscepticism, Cohesion Policy and European identity.
2. **Immigration and refugees.** Even if this might not be directly linked to the project, there is a lot of criticism on how the EU is handling the refugees' crisis. Since PERCEIVE will try to build a theory of cohesion in diversity, we should not use a language of exclusion of the refugee but underline the problematic aspects.
3. **Racism and far right movements.** These groups are very relevant for PERCEIVE because they tend to divide European citizens, dismantle European Identity and promote anti-Europeanism. We want to counter this kind of users explicitly.
4. **Terrorism.** We don't want to discuss this topic, the proportion of this phenomenon is far smaller than the refugees crisis, even though there is a large media impact.
5. **Import/export (TTIP related issues).** Harmonization of the EU legislation with other countries might translate into a lower standard of our products. This is something we don't want to discuss because it doesn't relate in any way with PERCEIVE. We do not explicitly deal with TTIP's related issues, not because they are not important, but because they are not the focus of PERCEIVE.
6. **Borders and people circulation within the EU.** PERCEIVE does not address this issue.
7. **EU integration process: real inequalities vs. cohesion/convergence.** Assessing the social and economic impact of Cohesion Policy is not an aim of the PERCEIVE project. We want make clear that Cohesion Policy is specifically implemented in order to eliminate inequalities among EU countries.
8. **EU democracy levels and rankings (EU Parliament vs EU Commission):** The project moves off from the awareness that there is a problem of perceived democratic deficit in the EU, yet we want to underline the fundamental role of EU Parliament Committees that work constantly to bring forth the citizens' rights.
9. **European citizenship and European citizen rights.** The diverse European cultures, do share a common identity somehow. Something more problematic, however, is the European citizenship as a list of rights to which we are entitled. Had any issue to emerge dealing with European citizenships and rights, we will refer to two sources (1) the Copenhagen criteria; (2) the European regulations, directives, decisions and recommendations, and the rulings of the

Court of Justice.

10. **European policies vs. European politics.** As we mentioned previously, we want PERCEIVE to be a place in which we discuss policies and, possibly, not political propaganda. We try to carefully redirect the discussion to policies' implementation.
11. **Elections and politics.** These themes are difficult to avoid, since they directly involve citizens. Yet, following the previous statement, we deal with policies and not with politics: we deal with the consequences of politics from a data driven point of view.
12. **Jobs creation policies.** When criticism arises about unemployment in the EU, we want to highlight what, on the contrary, the EU concretely does to create jobs through its programs.
13. **Funding programs.** Positive results of EU funded projects might not always be visible to citizens. Our answers on the topic should show that improvements are made and our project is going to be more effective on that task.
14. **How should the EU be spending money.** PERCEIVE does not deal with this issue (except for what concerns Cohesion Policy).
15. **Cases of failure/success for European projects?** PERCEIVE does not deal with this issue.

4.2 Communication personas

Once we have established our group targets, we develop three '**personas**' through which we want our voice to be spoken. In marketing, this technique aims at creating fictional characters that represent the different user types that might use a website, brand, or product in a similar way. These three characters have a name, a job, a nationality and a personality. Identifying personas will help us figuring out how to communicate and 'speak' to our targets in the most realistic way, by creating a content that meets their needs.

4.2.1 From targets to personas

Based upon our mapping, we created three personas specifically fit to address the three actual targets. Given the three targets analysed in chapter 3.1 three different personas are designed: Aleksy, who interacts and reaches out to the academics, Francesca, who dialogues with the practitioners, and finally Jan, someone who speaks to the more general public, but he is interested, informed and enthusiastic about the EU.

4.2.2 Aleksy speaks to the Euro Scientist

Persona

Aleksy is a 40 year old Polish researcher, with a Phd in Social Sciences. He has a critical approach to overconfident and simplistic opinions and, for this reason, he's neither a supporter or an opponent of Europeanism. He's against any type of flag holding.

Tone

- argumentative
- explorative
- curious and doubtful
- slightly sarcastic

Language

- academic
- theoretical
- complexity is allowed
- analytical

Purpose

Aleksy wants to cast light on doubts and convince both citizens and decision makers to base their opinions on actual data and to think in terms of cause-effect relationships. In this way he aims at eliminating misconceptions, busting myths, clichés and stereotypes. He enjoys to look for interesting data that can generate new points of view on current European issues.

4.2.3 Francesca speaks to the Euro Professional

Persona

Francesca is a 29 year old Italian project manager who works as project developer and writes European Projects for a private consultancy in Brussels. She is a firm supporter of Europeanism. As a consequence, she has a problem-solving approach towards EU controversial issues: she doesn't minimize EU problems but she tends to find practical solutions through management and policy advising.

Tone

- positive
- concrete
- optimistic
- pragmatic

Language

- technical
- practical
- specific
- efficient (short periods)

Purpose

Francesca likes to share useful strategies, techniques and tools to make other professionals' work in more efficient and impactful ways. She invests time to look for good practices (in terms of EU projects and policies) to get inspiration from and to discuss with her peers. She often attends useful workshops that keep her updated on the latest trends and practices.

4.2.4 Jan speaks to the Euro Hobbyist

Jan is a 36 year old Dutch surveyor with a full time job, he is always been politically active and has a vivid interest in everything that is European, mostly to discuss it with its family and colleagues. He is a believer and he maintains that Europeans have more in commons than what they think.

Tone

- positive
- enthusiast
- engaging
- passionate

Language

- simple
- vivid
- spontaneous
- ironic

Purpose

Jan wants to show his friends and family that Europe is a great idea, and convince everybody that complaining is not the way to solve problems. He looks for EU news but mostly on general press websites, not on specific professional channels. He is an opponent of populism and anti-European parties.

4.3.5 Personas interaction plan, overlapping areas and degree of Europeanism

Personas are not monolithic identities: they might interact with each other and share some characteristics. Both our hobbyist and researcher are interested in insightful contents, for different reasons and they also want to lead people towards more factual reasoning, avoiding stereotypes. This is not the aim of our professional, however, because she is detached from the mission of speculating on the EU.

In terms of European ideological support, all of our characters are Europeanist, yet with different shades and ideas. The hobbyist is a pure Europeanist, we use this voice only for public campaigns and to share some more positive and unexpected EU news on general channels (such as Facebook). Francesca, on the other hand, constantly working with the EU bureaucracy, has a negative opinion of the EU apparatus, sometimes inefficient, but she thinks EU is a great idea and works everyday to improve the situation through a very practical approach.

The researcher is neutral and critical, he doesn't have a definitive idea on the value of Europe. As an academic, he likes most of the European cultural values but knows very well that the EU has a strong economic nature and prefers to avoid biases and let data convince him.

5. Content Strategy

5.1 Intro: accessible progressivity from surface to depth

5.1.1 Content breakdown overview

PERCEIVE is a research project and thus it's complicated in its very nature. Nevertheless it has relevance for a wide spectrum of people, from citizens to highly specialized researchers and policy makers.

In order to represent this complexity at all levels, we need to apply a specific content strategy that allows for a better dissemination of different layers of content.

Progressivity is our keyword: there should be no isolated content. Indeed, we want to build a chain of networked content that ranges from easy interviews on current topics to academic papers and temporary findings through a project 'glossary' - i.e. PERCEIVE's EU Instant Glossary - where we want to gather all basic definitions to be used.

To achieve progressivity and cover different depth of content, we plan a simple and effective breakdown of the content that we want to produce, share and interlink:

Partners	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
Depth	low	mid	high (progressive)
Aim	attract, generate relevance.	inform, update, disseminate public deliverable and temporary finding.	produce shared understanding of project key definitions.
Timeline	constant, feed the editorial plan weekly.	linked to specific deliverable milestones.	landing content to be produced month 6-9 and used constantly throughout the projects.

5.1.2 Content breakdown: current issues

To the end of creating relevance for citizens and informing targets, we will share and comment current news on EU related topics respecting what is stated in the critical issues in paragraph

4.1.5.

The relation that the project needs to develop with current issues is vital to link it to reality, to immediate relevance with contemporary problems and to the pressure they are able to put on people's attention. On some specific channels, this activity will help to push project-related processes into wider threads of conversation (eg: Twitter discussions) thus presenting PERCEIVE project and its actions as a lively action on relevant matters.

For this reason, current issues are planned to create a constant communication carpet for the whole project, especially in the first two years, when temporary findings need to be related to emerging topics to generate more meaning.

In terms of editorial planning, monitoring and sharing of current EU-related or project-related news at a regional level is one of the main DCT task. BAM! will both monitor and collect content from DCT members to organize it on an editorial timeline in order to cover a day-by-day communication of the project.

5.1.3 Content breakdown: project development

A continuous stream of connection with current issues in EU policies and citizenship is helpful to generate relevance for project communication, but at the heart of the dissemination strategy must lie the project itself. The more project goals, deliverables and temporary findings get exposed, the more feedback they can get and the more expectations can be managed towards final papers and research outputs.

Project development contents are sub-divided into three main categories:

- **Research deliverables.** These are mandatory pieces of knowledge that the consortium needs to deliver at specific stages of the timeline. Public deliverables need to be shared publicly and listed on a specific download library on the project website. At the editorial planning level, every deliverable will be shared on different channels and social media groups depending on specific content and relevance.
- **Temporary findings.** Deliverables might be complex materials to be digested by communication channels. In order for them to be effective landing contents, we need to create a preparatory information thread that facilitate putting deliverables in context while generating specific expectations.
- **People, meeting and events.** PERCEIVE project is not only about research content, but also real people passionately investigating and exploring complex meanings around the perception of Europe. Therefore, for basic engagement to take place, we have to include PERCEIVE's staff in our communication in the most simple way: by showing periodically how they meet, work together, brainstorm and share their doubts and thoughts.

In terms of editorial planning, as described in details in the 'Actions' par. 6, project development dissemination actions are highly dependant on the DCT ability to produce a good connection with researchers at any point in time during the project. Making sure that temporary findings are

ready to be shared soon enough to generate curiosity around a specific deliverable.

We expect 'staff' related contents to get out once a week from month 5 on in order to present the international team working on the project. Once the overall presentation is accomplished, team related contents will be mainly used to personalize temporary findings and to build some storytelling around meetings and collective actions.

5.1.4 Content breakdown: EU Instant Glossary

What is the Cohesion Policy? What is a Smart City? What is Social Constructivism? PERCEIVE is not only a complex research project, but it also researches on topics that are already difficult to be understood by themselves with no further speculations. For this reason, we plan on building a website section dedicated to European jargon that might be difficult to understand in itself, thus constituting an engagement barrier for many. This section is named "EU Instant Glossary" and has several interlinked functions:

1. To be landing content for definition-based posts.
2. To develop a glossary function throughout the website: every time 'Cohesion Policy' (or any other keyword) is named in blog posts and interviews, it can be linked to the glossary to generate more comprehension. Same can be done on social media netiquettes, videos or within Twitter conversations when somebody mentions some project related keyword.
3. To help out search engine optimization (SEO) and organic search engine positioning of PERCEIVE within some specific themes.

The glossary is planned to be developed mainly during month 5-6 and to be enriched all along the project's progress, depending on temporary findings and deliverables' needs and context.

5.1.5 Management of comments and feedbacks

Beside project driven content, we need to develop a specific strategy on reactions that our communication targets may have to what we share. Especially considering that we will interact with current issues and, sometimes, with critical themes.

It is of utmost importance to understand that every engagement actions aims at triggering target reactions and that any reaction is generally a success - whether positive or negative, it is just a communication variable that needs to be addressed properly and managed according to the project identity guidelines.

Every social media channel will be equipped with a dedicated netiquette, also retrievable on the social media policy made available on the project website. The Social Media Policy is a fundamental piece of information that the project shares with its target in order to anticipate communication rules and baselines. Most of the content is summed up in the identity chapter of this document and includes specifications on acceptable and unacceptable contents, but it will also

includes more straightforward banning rules, such as the ones related to slander and offensive language.

5.2 Data engagement

At the heart of project development communication there is **data**. Data visualization is the most crucial variable to achieve PERCEIVE dissemination objectives, furthermore given that in our identity and brand definition we stated that we want to build an **evidence-based** communication.

For this reason PERCEIVE's communication will rely strongly on information graphics, also called **infographics**. These are graphic visual representations of information, data or knowledge intended to present information quickly and clearly. They can improve cognition by utilizing graphics to enhance the human visual system's ability to see patterns and trends.

Similar pursuits are information visualization, data visualization, statistical graphics, information design, or information architecture. Infographics have evolved in recent years to be for mass communication, and thus **are designed with fewer assumptions about the readers' knowledge base** than other types of visualizations.

A specific infographics syntax that relies on dots and shades has been developed coherently to the identity building and will be constantly used throughout the project to share temporary findings and deliverables.

The DCT will dedicate specific attention in gathering and sharing meaningful infographics to support current issues content sharing.

5.3 Image management

5.3.1 What types of images the project produces

Pictures should be produced so to return a brand coherent representation of the project. This means that they should mostly be:

- **High quality** (low quality is justified only for very specific situations where immediacy gets to be more important such as live tweeting during events).
- **Content oriented** - People should always be portrayed as they discuss, brainstorm, work, draw, sketch or any similar project-related activity. Pictures where it is possible to presume that the staff is passionate about what their doing will be preferred.

5.3.2 Privacy and partners representation

A specific form for image management and social media personal presence has been shared among partners to better know their preferences on privacy and personal involvement. Personal pictures and quotes of partners will be managed accordingly.

5.4 Project Presentations

Besides the website itself as primary source of information, we drafted two different kinds of project presentations that will be available online for download and as tools for quick and easy sharing of the project.

5.4.1 A short version for communication purpose

The first version is a two-pages document graphically illustrated that sums up the very essentials: it is an overview that gives a glimpse of the whole project. The language is very simple in order to be understood from all of our targets, it is also engaging in order to not only inform but get everybody interested, regardless the user's educational background.

The communication version aims at answering the basic questions: what? how? why? who? when?. Indeed, besides a short about and goals, we listed the partners and gave the contact information. It can be used for different purposes according to the different targets to whom the specific communication is directed; for example it can be sent attached to emails in order to disseminate the project and to get more institutions and organizations from the civil society on board.

5.4.2 A medium version for academic purpose

The second version is mainly directed towards academics or research users. In fact, it is a medium length document of 4-5 pages, a sort of executive summary, in which we illustrate the project by using an academic language, and we go more into details with the project structure and especially the research deliverables. The sections are typical of the academic paper structure: abstract, theoretical background, research objectives and actions (deliverables).

It can be downloaded from the website by those who prefer to print the information or are unwilling to navigate online in order to look for more details about PERCEIVE. The academic summary can also be attached to emails directed to academic conferences to apply as participants and speakers.

See attachment C.

6. Channel mix

6.1 From targets to channels: an overview

Channels are the means through which we reach our different targets and through which we talk as personas. On some channels you find a specific kind of target, on others you may not. In this way we can structure and differentiate our communication strategy, using a particular language on a dedicated channel to reach a particular audience. The channels that we are going to use are: a website, a website for blogging or news, Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, Mailchimp, YouTube, Flickr and Academia.edu.

6.1.2 Website

The PERCEIVE website works as a landing hub for all of our targets, but different sections of the website are dedicated to different targets.

Reason why

It will host the vast majority of original contents.

Aims:

- Explain the project aims
- Explain the project structure
- Get to know the partners

Target relevance

It works as landing hub for all targets.

Personas balance:

- The website mainly uses Aleksy's voice to keep a neutral, technical and critical approach on all standard descriptive contents
- A bit of Jan is used for headlines and parts aimed at the general public such as the 'non-academic' about and the contact session. It is important to leave to Jan some bits of the home page too, because we don't want him to think that the content is inaccessible or incomprehensible.

Content structure:

- Progressive
- Can be long

6.1.3 Website blog/news

Reason why

It will provide medium-depth personal contents to feed social media and other channels. A blog would personify the project with interviews and partners' stories and it's a chance to connect project content to present issues through comments and analysis on current events.

Aims:

- Provide new landing contents for social media
- Give a medium level of engagement

Target relevance:

- Works on professionals and hobbyists
- Less relevant for researchers

Personas balance:

- The blog will have different threads, but it mainly uses Jan's voice to keep a warm style of communication for current issues and interviews.
- In depth contents and projects temporary deliverable can have an 'Aleksy's corner' allowing for a second level in depth view.
- A specific blog thread will be dedicated to tips and tricks for professionals with Francesca's voice.

Content structure

Blog content needs to be narrative and engaging. If in depth content is available it is fine to use the blog to share it, but it can only be a second level and a narration has to be developed to introduce it.

6.1.4 Facebook

Reason why

Facebook represents the chance to catch the general public and to communicate at the simplest and direct level.

Aims:

- Get people interested in the project
- Overall, get the project known

Target relevance

Facebook aims primarily at EU Hobbyists and practitioners.

Personas balance:

- Jan talks, because we don't want to use a specific language (academic or technical), not understandable by everyone;

- However, we don't want to be too simplistic, so also Francesca, can produce contents more technical contents
- Aleksy's voice should be avoided on this channel

Content structure

Facebook content needs to be designed as 'easily shareable'. Which means it has to be easy to understand and identify at a glance leading to in-depth, more precise contents through a clearcut call to action. Good examples are:

- a. Catchy quotes coming both from project partners and current events
- b. Visually engaging contents that give an easy representation of something complex
- c. Emotionally triggering photos and contents on current issues
- d. With a different edge, also storytelling photos of partners working provide good personal 'real' content for Facebook

6.1.5 LinkedIn

Reason why

LinkedIn is increasingly becoming relevant for professional networking but also sharing latest insights sharing. Groups are a key element of LinkedIn: they allow for specific professional target communication and engagement.

Aims:

- Get the project known as a good practice in the European management field
- Share research temporary findings

Target relevance

- More relevant for professional /less relevant for academics
- Mostly non-relevant for hobbyists

Personas Balance

Francesca talks because she can find her professional hub right here, thorough groups in particular.

Alesky is also interested in LinkedIn, but mainly for networking, not for specific academic content - you hardly find it here - but maybe he reads in depth insight (interesting articles)

6.1.6 Twitter

Reason why

Engage with influencers on two separate levels, reach out for professionals and engage with individual influencers and decision makers.

Aims:

- Collect a wide number of influencers tweeting on specific EU topics and engage with them
- Engage with professionals

- Engage with decision makers
- Keep track of project-relevant current issues

Target relevance

- Communication mainly dedicated to professionals
- Highlight and project steps also dedicated to decision makers and institutional representatives

Personas Balance

- Mostly Francesca
- Jan only for current events' response and share of project's findings

Content structure

- Mostly share other channels useful tips and contents
- Quick-share of data highlights from research and temporary findings

6.1.7 Mailchimp

Reason why

Newsletter tool to manage different types of mailing lists (internal and external)

Aims:

To share updates on the project in a dedicated environment (events, temporary papers, video, interviews, etc.).

Target relevance:

We can reach all the targets through lists you can differentiate your newsletter.

Personas Balance

- Alesky talks about temporary research findings, conferences, academic events
- Francesca talks about innovative aspects about PERCEIVE's management and communication strategies
- Jan shares interviews, engaging contents, "How are EU?" campaign content
- Jan contents can be also send by all the personas, because they relate to the project as a whole

Content structure

Monthly or every two weeks, depending on the timeline of the project.

6.1.8 YouTube

Reason why

To store an easily browsable collection of project videos.

Aims:

- Make video content available
- Promote campaign video through YouTube 'True View' system

Target relevance:

- More relevant for EU citizens and general public
- Some video threads could be useful for professionals as well

Content structure:

PERCEIVE's videos must be very short and easy to understand: they shouldn't handle too many concepts at a time, if it ends up being too long it needs to be broken down into more clips.

6.1.9 Flickr

Reason why:

To store an easily browsable collection of project images, can be shared among partners or publicly.

Aims:

- Create emotional engagement related to the project for partners (team building) for private use
- Proof of meetings etc. for deliverables
- To create a more real perception of the project for public use

Target relevance:

All targets, depending on the type of picture

Personas Balance

- Jan prefers more emotional pictures (big smiles)
- Francesca a more professional and work related activities (taking notes, etc.)
- Aleksy likes pictures of academic conferences when you can catch slides, presentations, etc.

Content structure:

- Events
- Research activities
- Focus groups
- In almost every picture PERCEIVE brand must be visible

6.1.10 Academia.edu

Reason why

On this social media you can share papers, temporary findings, academic materials in general. It is useful for networking with professors, researchers and students worldwide. Moreover on this channel is possible to create 'sessions', that are explicit invitations to receive feedbacks on a specific working paper/document.

Aims:

- Make the project known in the academia
- Share temporary findings and papers
- Connect with other researchers on the topic
- Receive early feedbacks

Target relevance

Only academics and students

6.2 Channel differentiation matrix

Target priority	Facebook	Twitter	LinkedIn	YouTube	Flickr	Partners	Mailchimp
Academic	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Professionals	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Citizens	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

- canale preferenziale
- canale compatibile
- canale incompatibile

7. Actions

7.1 Access, inform, engage: action scopes and aims

Communication and dissemination actions are strictly related to targets and project aims. As part of the H2020 framework, engagement and dissemination actions have a key role in determining the project success or failure.

Coherently with communication aims and project timeline, planned actions will be subdivided into 4 main categories:

1. **Enabling of landing content.** These are actions aimed at switching on channels that can host contents dedicated to explain the project structure, timings and aims.
2. **Develop a project communication network.** This means mapping and reaching out for a target segmented audience, introducing project aims and structure, present partners and purposes and discuss project-related current issues.
3. **Temporary findings and public deliverables sharing.** Draft and follow a dedicated timeline to share PERCEIVE's temporary findings and project deliverables in the most impactful way, extracting meaning at different levels. Having something more meaningful to narrate about the project beside its structure, it is the third step that allows for a **wider engagement campaign** to take place.
4. **Project output communication.** Sharing and disseminating the of project research outputs at different levels.

Following the project timeline we can put these categories in subsequent steps:

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4
Landing content	Develop project communication network	Temporary findings sharing	Project output communication

Communication's Activities Calendar

We also plan to organise five dedicated events to present our preliminary and full results to our stakeholders (for those people unable to attend in person, we will release the proceedings and we will offer online access through the project and partners' websites):

- **September 26 - 27 2016 (month 1):** A kick-off meeting was held in Bologna, Italy, where all the partners presented the general method, the timescale of the project and the expected outcomes of PERCEIVE. In this meeting we discussed and validated the overall strategy of the project. As leader of the WP7, BAM! produced communication materials based on PERCEIVE's brand identity for dissemination. Notebooks, pens, flyers and shoppers had been given and shipped to partners in order to increase the project's visibility in their universities and institutions, and during focus groups. In particular, we ordered two totems that need to be located in the University of Bologna, the project leader.
- **Month 12:** a conference in Gothenburg, Sweden, to present the results of the survey at citizen level on perceptions and attitudes toward EU and to validate the preliminary analysis held in WP1 and WP2.
- **Month 24:** a scientific workshop in Vienna, Austria, to analyse the main academic results of WP3 and WP5 with researchers and to reinforce academic impact.
- **Month 26:** a conference in Bucharest, Romania, organised by the World Bank, member of the Advisory Board, targeted for policy-makers, practitioners and other stakeholders in order to validate the first policy recommendations. The event includes a closed-door workshop with 10 policymakers from the case-study regions aimed at presenting and getting feedback on the beta version of the simulation model of WP6 - a co-creation phase.
- **Second workshop:** a communication of possible behaviours emerging from the model.
- **Month 36:** one final conference in Brussels, Belgium, to present the results of the project, put the highlight on the third-party partners that will have substantially contributed during the project and evaluate the emerged policy recommendations with policymakers and practitioners.

7.2 Progressive engagement on targets

Each of the four categories include actions dedicated to different targets. To sum up:

Partners	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4
Academic		Create the bases to update academics on research progresses.	Share the progress of temporary findings and research directions, ask for related research outputs.	Organize in depth workshops on project findings. Share papers on academic platforms. Develop activities based on digital simulation.
Professional	Project description	Discuss EU projects impact with LMA and the networks of EU professionals. Develop a project motion graphic video to support a basic awareness campaign.	Share infographics on temporary findings and develop discussion on their impact.	Develop a tech list of main issues influencing positively or negatively EU projects impact.
Hobbyists		Engage with EU update and communication outlets (as second level targets) to develop media partnerships or have them talk about the project.	Share interviews and develop easy infographics. Startup the "How are EU?" campaign to direct EU hobbyists towards a deeper project understanding through temporary findings.	Develop a press release to share the project findings and the digital simulation with communication outlets and topic related news outlets.

7.3 Focus on project's temporary findings and public deliverables

We will schedule a series of action in relation to project's temporary findings and public deliverables. In the following paragraph, we'll give you a timeline of communication's actions that will be undertaken and a directed to the different kinds of targets listed above.

The idea is to gradually inform about a specific topic when temporary findings emerge from the research, before the deliverable deadline, and validate or not when further final results are

available. This because we need to get your channels in the loop of the project, regardless the finalization of the deliverables. To do so, we listed temporary findings and and deliverables, and related expected due date, followed by the communication actions' description. In this way, we will be able to identify thematic macro-areas within the project development. This macro-areas contains a series of key concepts and words that will be collected in **PERCEIVE's EU Instant Glossary**.

7.3.1 Phase I “Get the project started”: EU Cohesion Policy, smart cities, urban policies and social constructivism breakdown

Month 4

Temporary Findings

WP4 - Dataset on Smart Cities along with preliminary maps and conceptual analysis

Month 5

Temporary Findings

WP1 - How does Europe contribute to our regional development? Task 1.1 collects data on thousands of projects supported by Cohesion Policy across our case-study regions. Moreover we will have preliminary quantitative insights on the communication activities undertaken by Local Managing Authorities.

WP4 - Preliminary report on smart cities

WP5 - What does it mean to feel European? First insights regarding the importance of a social constructivist approach to identification with EU and European Identity.

Deliverable

WP1, UNIBO - Database of the Cohesion Policy projects managed by Local Managing Authorities and a SWOT analysis on the governance models in the selected case study regions in the programming period 2007-2013.

Month 4-5

Communication actions

- We will inform about Cohesion Policy's basic concepts: what kind of policy is it and how is it implemented. We will also discuss Local Managing Authorities: what is their role? Do people know about it? What are their communication activities? The main tools that will be used are PERCEIVE's EU Instant Glossary and blog posts. In relation to case studies we will develop infographics and a map of the project's regions. These contents will be disseminated at different target levels through social media share.
- We will take into account what emerges from SWOT analysis, in the different regions, regarding the governance models. In this case, SWOT analysis will be broken down for editorial purposes and multiple social posts.
- We will introduce and define the concept of smart cities on the EU Instant Glossary and use preliminary maps and conceptual analysis to build infographics and engaging maps for blog posts and social media sharing.
- We will approach the European identity by breaking down the concept of social constructivism. In this case a series of blog post on the first insights from WP5 will be our

reference in order to explain the complexity of cultural and social environment's influence on citizens' Europeanness (first, as a general theory, and second as related to the EU).

Month 6

Temporary Findings

WP4 - Preliminary Report on the synergies between EU Cohesion Policy and rural development policies

WP5 (up to month 10) - Backstage of data collecting process. The work package has to collect newspapers' articles, tweets and blog as well as communications from central EU offices and financed projects' abstracts. The team will be able to offer a stream of backstage in order to create hype for the results. At this stage, indeed, we can only discuss about collecting data.

Deliverables

WP4, PBS - Report on Urban policies for building smart cities

WP5, WU - Short contribution (report) to be used in dissemination events about the empirical relevance of a social constructivist and discursive approach to EU identity emergence and integration

Communication actions

What are urban policies? How urban policies contribute to the smart cities development? New keyword for EU Instant Glossary, a dedicated blog post and following social media sharing.

- Introducing rural development policies, definition and possible synergies with Cohesion Policy, through blog posts and social media sharing.
- Social constructivism, to be continued. From theory to empirical evidence: WP5 temporary findings will be used to keep the conversation going on the topic, more blog posts.

We will start discussing sentiments on EU thanks to social media, web, newspapers as well as official communication data, which can be finalized in a first blog post and definition of keywords on the EU Instant Glossary, and then in the social media sharing.

7.3.2 Phase II “Results of interaction”: Focus Groups on Cohesion Policy implementation and its communication strategy

Month 9

Temporary Findings

WP1 - Early insights from focus groups regarding implementation schemes of Cohesion Policy. How is it managed in the planning and execution phase? How do different bodies and actors cooperate? To what extent are local needs taken into account? Some comparative insights and/or anecdotes from single regional case studies.

WP3 - Early insights from focus groups regarding communication strategies enacted by LMAs. I think we can provide some comparative insights and/or anecdotes from single regional case studies.

Deliverable

WP4, PBS - Report on the synergies between EU Cohesion Policy and rural development

policies

Month 10

Deliverable

WP3, WU - Qualitative report on the impact and effectiveness of communication strategies from the semi structured interviews with Cohesion Policy practitioners (including third party partners in the consortium), written by each partner.

Month 9-10

Communication actions:

- Insights from focus groups will be used to show comparative results in case studies. In this case we can start sharing some interviews and quotes thorough blog posts, yet only qualitative content not quantitative.
- How do Cohesion Policy and Rural policies interact? It will be described with a blog post and related keywords on the glossary, shared on targeted LinkedIn groups.
- Direct mailing to LMAs.
- A second, more quantitative take, on what emerge from the interviews during focus groups and interactions that can be used for more communication materials such as video interviews, pictures and quotes, a map of communication strategies effectiveness perception.
- When do communication strategies are really effective? Without considering the data but by only by gathering discussions and opinions about it: interviews of EU communication officers and project managers with a "5 tips from" format, four guest post blogs.
- Data collecting on EU sentiments: keep the editorial plan going as stated previously on month 6 - continuing background activity.

7.3.3 PHASE III "Some Guidelines": First Recommendations on Cohesion Policy from the project

Month 11

Temporary Finding

WP4 - Preliminary Report on Smart Cities and Resilience

Month 12

Temporary Findings

WP1 - To what extent do European citizens know about Cohesion Policy? To what extent do they trust in European institutions? Are national or regional governments better trusted? What is the support for redistribution policies? To what extent are these views and perceptions shared across different regions? Preliminary insights from the citizens level survey in T1.3.

WP3 - Data regarding closed-ended questionnaires sent to LMAs (task 3.2). Something in the line of: how many questionnaires sent, percentage of respondents, more active LMAs, etc. Descriptive info regarding the process, more than the actual results.

Deliverables

WP2, UGOT - Report including the database development and implementation and how it supports all the project WPs

WP4, PBS - Report on Smart Cities and Resilience

Month 12

Event: a conference in **Gothenburg**, Sweden, to present the results of the survey at citizen level on perceptions and attitudes toward EU and to validate the preliminary analysis held in WP1 and WP2.

Month 14

Deliverable

WP3, WU - Qualitative report with main findings from the interviews

WP4, IAFE NRI - Report on the policy recommendations on how to integrate Cohesion Policy with Urban and Rural policies

WP5, UNIBO - Database of the topics and sentiments to be made available on-line for further research

Month 10 -14

Communication actions:

- Consolidation of the communication thread on smart cities: four internal blog posts with related glossary items, dissemination and interaction on LinkedIn groups and intersection with Twitter dialogues and influencers on the theme, four guest post blogs. How smart are the cities in our case studies? Now we can build individual city infographics and collective infographics, targeting LinkedIn groups and Twitter threads.
- With the recommendations on how to integrate Rural policies and Cohesion Policy, we can draft a blog post for practitioners and decision/policy makers, an update for academics with link to paper download.
- What are the topics and sentiments online in different countries? A qualitative take, now we can build infographics and icons to illustrate the different sentiments (good for social media communities and digital press release to media partners).
- Preliminary findings on citizens and info on Local Managing Authorities. In the first case we can share qualitative data at citizens' level (quotes, etc.), whereas in the second we can continue to develop our thread on LMAs, from general info to specific identification (for EU practitioners).

7.3.4 Phase IV: "Citizens perception of EU and role of new media in EU project"

Month 15

Temporary Findings

WP3 - Insights regarding the use of rhetoric by LMAs and Central EU communication offices: anecdotes, first insights... In particular insights regarding the use of new media vs. traditional media.

Deliverables

WP2, UB - Report of the spatial analysis results of the heterogeneous multidimensional determinants of EU citizens perception at the regional case study level

WP4, IEA - Report on the comparative analysis of experts' and citizens' perceptions and views

WP5, UNIBO - Production of a report discussing (including visualizing topographic maps of meanings) the emergent topics in identity relevant discourse at the different levels

Month 16

Temporary Findings

WP5 - First results of the statistical analysis aimed at testing interregional variations.

Deliverable

WP3, WU - Descriptive report on the specific role of new media in EU financed projects' communication strategies

Month 17

Deliverables

WP2, UB - Report on the construction of the EQI indicator - Qualitative report with main findings from the survey and discussion of comparative results from the application of the indicator of perception in the different case study regions

WP5, WU - Report of the comparative analysis of the correlation between topics emergent from regional discourses on the one hand, and the awareness and perceptions of the EU (from Eurobarometer) on the other hand

Month 15-17

Communication actions

- Development of an accurate map with citizens perceptions in different countries, and topographic maps of meanings. We will build infographics, maps, and video animation to illustrate research results. It is a very good output for social media communities and digital press release to media partners. Four blog posts from the findings will be online, coming out from four map highlights and unexpected vs predictable data output.
- Definition of the new media as a keyword for EU Instant Glossary and selection of quotes from the report that highlight the efficiency or inefficiency of their use by the projects. We will draft blog posts accordingly.
- Rhetoric vs impact: a thread of interviews with new media influencers
- Rhetoric vs impact: some case studies of successful new media usage
- What is the EQI indicator? How does it apply to the case studies? To answer these questions we will draft a specific blog post with infographic icons and PERCEIVE's EU Instant Glossary.
- In this phase, we will continuously keep track of emergent topics and citizens perception of the EU, and update with blog posts and social media sharing.

7.3.5 PHASE V “Reflective engagement”: campaign launch and impact of communication strategies on EU appreciation

Month 18

Temporary Findings

WP3 - First results of the analysis that relates impact and effectiveness on EU projects' communication on one hand and investments and rhetorical strategies on the other hand. This temporary findings are really a preview on the deliverable D3.4.

Month 21

Temporary Findings

WP3 - Reflection on the dynamic dimension of awareness. First results of the comparison between secondary historical data and our data.

Month 22

Deliverables

WP2, UNIBO - Report on the probabilistic model of estimation of citizens' identification with the EU project and ranking of the case study regions

WP3, WU - Report on the statistical analysis of communication efforts' impact and effectiveness on citizens' awareness and appreciation of EU financed projects

Month 18-22

Communication actions

- Campaign “**How are EU?**” Launch
Gamification: quiz-game on European citizenship and European value. Bring people to relative opinion position towards
 5. Emotional opinion communication videos & campaign with main concept “we share more than what divides us”
 6. Compared quotes and interviews on “What does EU means to you?” from both EU citizens and non EU citizens
 7. More exploitation of media partnership to interview different audiences and feed the campaign
- Quantitative data on communication strategies' impact on citizens will be used for infographics and quotes.

Events:

- Month 24: a scientific workshop in Vienna, Austria, to analyse the main academic results of WP3 and WP5 with researchers and to reinforce academic impact;

7.3.6 PHASE VI “Getting into the virtual simulation”:

Month 26

Temporary Findings

WP6 - Cause-effect diagram in which we describe the phenomena we want to explain, this is called system archetype: a graph that captures the very archetypal structure of the problem. Very effective visual representation.

Deliverable

WP6, UNIBO - Report on causal qualitative model

Month 28

Deliverable

WP2, UB - Report on the results of the convergence analysis of EU citizens’ identification with the EU project from 1995 up to now.

Month 26-28

Communication actions

- We will draft a technical explanation of the digital simulation for academics and a simpler visual representation for the general public, both through blog posts with related glossary items. This kind of content fits also for social media sharing: in the first case for LinkedIn and in the second for Facebook and Twitter.
- A visual timeline of the citizens’ identification with the EU in the last 20 years can be illustrated along with a blog post, and a quick video easily sharable on social media.
- Milestone extraction end debate over specific milestones

Events:

- Month 26: A conference in Bucharest, Romania, organised by the World Bank, member of the Advisory Board, targeted for policy-makers, practitioners and other stakeholders in order to validate the first policy recommendations. The event includes a closed-door session with 10 policymakers from the case-study regions aimed at presenting and getting feedback on the beta version of the simulation model of WP6.

3.3.7 Phase VII “Policy Papers and Digital Simulation implementation”

Month 30

Deliverable

WP7, UNIBO - Policy Brief (1): Guidelines on Cohesion Policies Implementation

Month 32

Deliverable

WP2, UGOT - Report on the influence of the perceptions of corruption and governance on EU citizens’ support for EU Cohesion Policy

Month 33

Deliverable

WP6, UNIBO - Digital simulation interface

Month 34

Deliverables

WP6, UNIBO - Report with analysis of model behaviour and scenario analysis

WP7, UNIBO - Policy Brief (2): Guidelines on Cohesion Policies Communication

Month 30-36

Communication actions:

- The Policy Brief on Cohesion Policy implementation is mainly directed to practitioners, so the written papers will be integrated with visually engaging infographics, to be shared on LinkedIn or newsletter. The guidelines can thus be illustrated with bullet points 'how to' style for social media shared on EU professionals social media hubs (blogs, forums and groups).
- Four blog posts on temporary findings and report highlights (+ relevant glossary items)
- Four guest blog posts, written interview with influencers on the corruption theme
- Go live of a fully functional interactive graphic simulator of the parametric correlation between the research variables identified and the data collected during the project (D7.3)
- Organize a simulation workshop with key stakeholders, journalists and media partner
- Organize debate threads on social media groups
- Guidelines for practitioners on how to communicate and infographics and highlights for social media
- Organize a practitioners workshop to share key operational findings
- Share with practitioners social media hubs and foster debate

Event:

- **Month 36:** One final conference in Brussels, Belgium, to present the results of the project, put the highlight on the third-party partners that will have substantially contributed during the project and evaluate the emerged policy recommendations with policymakers and practitioners.

8. Key Performance Indicators

8.1 Overview

As part of the internal performance evaluation process, and given as a preparatory process for the final evaluation we embed a series of performance indicators that will help BAM! and the DCT to better understand the effectiveness trend of PERCEIVE communication and dissemination strategy.

In order to have a more complete approach to result analysis we will take to account four different performance indicators:

KPI	Performance Question	Measurement
8.2 Knowledge accessibility	Are information available at different levels of depth? Are they easy to find and understand?	Website pop up short questionnaire (eg: job title + how do you find the project clear 1-5?) For academic dissemination we will measure how many papers and temporary findings are shared and accessed throughout the project.
8.3 Quantitative reach	How many people have been reached by PERCEIVE content? For how long?	Through different channels' analytics platforms and reach goalsetting.
8.4 Qualitative reach	How are specific target reached by PERCEIVE content? How are they responding? How much do specific targets consume PERCEIVE communication contents?	Beside the different channels' analytics platforms we'll use direct contact reactions as a qualitative assessment method.
8.5 Engagement	How do specific targets react to PERCEIVE contents? What kind of contribution do they give in sharing communication actions?	Different channels' analytics platform measure attention spikes and engagement rates.

8.2 Knowledge accessibility

As stated in the Communication objectives, we need PERCEIVE to be accessible on multiple levels of depth. We will be using instant pop-up questionnaires on the website to check whether we're accomplishing multiple depth accessibility of contents.

Are people finding what they need to on our website? Are project goals stated clear? Four dif-

ferent aspects of the project will be mapped through instant pop up during website navigation. Every user should not get more than one question every six month, so that the pop up questionnaire does not conflict with ease of navigation.

8.3 Quantitative reach

The most straightforward way to measure communication performance is to count heads. Thanks to social media insights and Google Analytics it's easy to track down who's seeing our contents with a further breakdown:

- Geographic spread
- Age groups
- Referral and source of visit
- Most visited contents
- User flow and relevance patterns

Thanks to this tool we'll always have a real time idea of how project communication is performing in terms of overall number of people reached.

8.4 Qualitative reach

Beside quantitative data, web analytics tool can also track down a number of qualitative aspects. First of all, the source of visit on website and the user flow allow us to retrace what target groups the visitors belong to, their interest in the project and their level of knowledge on project themes.

Thanks to these tools we'll be able to set specific qualitative goals on the different platform and have a real time reporting of the qualitative performance of the different action.

A key role for spotting out different target qualitative reach will be taken by MailChimp integration with Google Analytics that allows for a real time monitoring of direct mail reactions and interactions.

8.5 Engagement

The final level of measurement focus on the interaction that the project is able to generate towards different targets. This specific indicators will help us understanding how much the different targets contribute with the project by sharing contents, commenting and feeding new contents for project communication through gamification platforms.

Project Engagement will be measured on different specific aspects

- Social media engagement: number of people commenting, contributing and sharing content

on PERCEIVE social media platform

- Content engagement: number of 'guest bloggers' involved in the process of creating new content for the project and that will, in the final stages of the project, show up or show interest for project PERCEIVE workshops.
- Gamification engagement: the number of people actively engaging with the "How are EU?" campaign.

8.5 Internal Communication Performance

We are using specific project management tools to be able to track down internal communication processes as well. Thanks to these tool we will be able to produce an internal communication report to measure performances in terms of communication content produced and shared internally during the project.

Attachment A: Mapping

ACADEMICS								
Learned Societies								
Organization	Type	Location	Media Partner	Website	Facebook	Twitter	Linkedin	Contact
RSA - Regional Studies Association	learned society	Seaford, UK	•	http://www.regionalstudies.org/	•	•	•	klara.sobekova@regionalstudies.org, Communication officer
EURAM - European Academy of Management	learned society	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://www.euram-online.org/	•	•	•	Edoardo Mollona and Luca Pareschi (UNIBO)
EGOS - European Group for Organization Studies	learned society	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://www.egosnet.org/	•	•	•	Edoardo Mollona and Luca Pareschi (UNIBO)
AOM - Academy of Management	learned society	NY, USA	•	http://aom.org/	•	•	•	
ESA - European Sociological Association	learned society	Paris, France	•	http://www.europeansociology.org/	•	•	•	
ERSA - European Regional Science Association	learned society	Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium	•	http://ersa.org/	•	•	•	maristella.angotzi@ersa.org, communication officer
NOMISMA	learned society	Bologna, Italy	•	http://www.nomisma.it/	•	•	•	Andrea.Goldstein@nomisma.it
EAEPE- European Association of Evolutionary Political Economy	learned society	Erfurt, Germany	•	http://eaepe.org/	•	•	•	marco.raberto@unige.it
Stockholm Environmental Institute	learned society	Rome, Italy	•	http://www.systemdynamics.it/	•	•	•	info@systemdynamics.it
Research Groups								
ESA RN6 - Critical Political Economy	ESA research network		•	http://www.europeansociology.org/research-networks/rn6-critical-political-economy/70-rn6-themes-of-recent-conferences.html	•	•	•	Luca Pareschi (UNIBO)
ESA RN26 - Sociology of Social Policy	ESA research network		•	http://www.europeansociology.org/research-networks/rn26-sociology-of-social-policy.html	•	•	•	

Stockholm Environmental Institute	Research institute	Stockholm, Sweden	•	https://www.sei-international.org/about-sei	•	•	•	Irene Monasterolo (independent researcher)
Conferences								
EURAM	Conference	Glasgow, Scotland	•		•	•	•	
EGOS	Conference	2017 Copenhagen, Denmark	•		•	•	•	
AOM	Conference	2017 Atlanta, USA	•		•	•	•	
ESA	Conference	2017 Athens, Greece	•		•	•	•	
ERSA	Conference	2017 Groninger, The Netherlands	•	https://ersa.eventsair.com/QuickEventWebsitePortal/2017-ersa-congress/official-website	•	•	•	maristella.angotzi@ersa.org, communication officer
EAEPE	Conference	2017 Budapest, Hungary	•	http://eaepe.org/?page=events&side=annual_conference	•	•	•	
Professors								
University	Department	Location		Website				
Boston University	Center for the Study of Europe	Boston, USA	•	https://www.bu.edu/polisci/people/faculty/vivienschmidt/	•	•	•	vschmidt@bu.edu
University of Zurich	Department of Banking	Zurich, Switzerland	•	http://www.bf.uzh.ch/cms/en/battiston.stefano.html	•	•	•	stefano.battiston@uzh.ch
Unviersita' Roma 3	Jean Monnet chair of European Economic integration	Rome, Italy	•	http://host.uniroma3.it/centri/jeanmonnet/	•	•	•	pasquale.tridico@uniroma3.it
PRACTITIONERS								
EU Institutional Architecture								
Organization	Type	Location	Media Partner	Website	Facebook	Twitter	Linkedin	
European Parliament Committee on Regional Development	committee	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://www.europarl.europa.eu/committees/it/regi/home.html	•	•	•	
EU Regional & Urban Policy	policy		•	http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/	•	•	•	
European Parliament Committee on Employment and Social Affairs	committee	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://www.europarl.europa.eu/committees/en/empl/home.html	•	•	•	
European Parliament Committee on Industry, Research, Telecoms & Energy	committee	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://www.europarl.europa.eu/committees/en/itre/home.html	•	•	•	

European Parliament Committee on Culture and Education	committee	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://www.europarl.europa.eu/committees/it/cult/home.html	•	•	•
The European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT)	agency	Budapest, Hungary	•	https://eit.europa.eu/	•	•	•
The Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency or EACEA	agency	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/index_en.php	•	•	•
Eurofound	agency	Dublin, Ireland	•	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/	•	•	•
European Research Council	agency	Brussels, Belgium	•	https://erc.europa.eu	•	•	•
Commission on Employment, Social Affairs & Inclusion	commission	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://ec.europa.eu/social/home.jsp?langId=en	•	•	•
European Committee of the Regions	committee	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://cor.europa.eu/en/Pages/home.aspx	•	•	•
European Economic and Social Committee	committee	Brussels, Belgium	•	http://www.eesc.europa.eu/?i=portal.en.home	•	•	•

People	Role	Website	Facebook	Twitter	Linkedin	Contact
Corina Crețu	European commissioner for Regional Policy	http://ec.europa.eu/commission/2014-2019/cretu_en	•	•	•	
Marianne Thyssen	European Commissioner for Employment, Social Affairs, Skills and Labour Mobility		•	•	•	

Local Managing Authorities (LMAs)

Name	Type	Location	Media Partner	Website	Facebook	Twitter	Linkedin	Contact
Ministero dello sviluppo economico – Direzione generale per gli incentive alle imprese	ministry	Italy	•	http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/	•	•	•	
Regione Emilia-Romagna	region	Italy	•	http://fesr.regione.emilia-romagna.it/	•	•	•	
Managing Authority ROP - Ministry of Regional Development and Public Administration	ministry	Romania	•	http://www.mdrap.ro/	•	•	•	
Agenzia per la Coesione Territoriale	agency	Italy	•	http://www.agenziacoesione.gov.it/				

EU Lobbying Architecture

Organizations	Type	Media Partner	Website	Facebook	Twitter	Linkedin	Contact
Confindustria delegation to the EU	delegation	Bruxelles, Belgium	•				
Debating Europe	think-tank	Bruxelles, Belgium	•	http://www.debatingeurope.eu/	•	•	•

Friends of Europe	think-tank	Bruxelles, Belgium	•	http://www.friendsofeurope.org/	•	•	•
European Movement International	nonprofit org	Bruxelles, Belgium	•	http://europeanmovement.eu/	•	•	•
European students' union	nonprofit org	Bruxelles, Belgium	•	https://www.esu-online.org/about/	•	•	•
ECIT (a Foundation on European Citizens' Rights, Involvement and Trust)	think-tank	Bruxelles, Belgium	•	http://ecit-foundation.eu/	•	•	•
The European Citizen Action Service (ECAS)	nonprofit org	Bruxelles, Belgium	•	http://ecas.org/	•	•	•
EuVisions	think-tank	Turin, Italy	•	http://www.euvisions.eu/	•	•	•
OpenCoesione	nonprofit org	Italy	•	http://www.opencoessione.gov.it/	•	•	•
A scuola di OpenCoesione	nonprofit org	Italy	•	http://www.ascuoladiopencoessione.it/	•	•	•
EU Project Management Professional							
HorizonTap - tapping into the knowledge of project managers of EU-funded projects/networks	LinkedIn group		•		•	•	•
The European Community of Project Managers and Administrators (ECPMA)	nonprofit org		•	•	•	•	•
The National Contact Point for Horizon 2020	organization		•		•	•	•
EU Digital Blog	online platform		•	https://blogs.ec.europa.eu/eu-digital/	•	•	•
"H2020 SSH" Social Innovation Research, Socio-Economic Sciences and Humanities	LinkedIn group		•	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4427026	•	•	•
Europe Project Forum	organization	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	•	http://www.euprojectforum.eu/	•	•	•
European Certification and Qualification association	Training school	Krems, Austria	•	http://www.ecqa.org/index.php?id=32	•	•	•
Pixel - International Education and Training Institution	Training school	Florence, Italy	•	http://europlan.pixel-online.org/EPM_index.php	•	•	•

Attachment B:

Dissemination and Communication Team (DCT) Roles and Functions

DCT Mission

In order to reach all the stakeholders and ensure an effective dissemination, we have created a Dissemination and Communication Team (DCT) that includes a member from each partner of the Consortium, under the leadership of BAM! and UNIBO. This team is responsible for internal and external communications and ensures the effective dissemination of the internal and final results involving all the relevant stakeholders. Each member of the team will be monitoring host country policy development and needs, sharing policy-relevant data from their unit with the rest of the team and reporting back to their own unit on important policy developments in the project.

The DCT is also in charge of monitoring news stories related to the project's topics so we will be able to prepare in due time reports and press releases. The DCT will thus be in charge for the networking with media professionals, the constant monitoring of news related to the project's topics and the issuing of materials and press releases aimed at guaranteeing an adequate media coverage that will potentially expand the pool of stakeholders reached by the project's findings.

List of members

Lucia Baruzzi (Coordinator)	BAM!	WP7
Davide Baruzzi (Strategy Supervisor)	BAM!	WP7
Luca Pareschi (Content Supervisor)	UNIBO	WP3, WP5
Vicente Royuela	UB	WP2, WP4
Nicholas Charron	UGOT	WP1, WP2
Vitaliano Barberio	WU	WP3, WP5
Gianpiero Torrisi	PBS	WP4
Elisabeta Rosu	IAE	ALL
Barbara Wieliczko	IAFE-NRI	WP1, WP4

Roles

The role of BAM! is to coordinate the DCT and manage communication and dissemination operations and actions, whereas UNIBO will supervise the relevance of communication content and actions. The other DCT members will provide content through the editorial planning process

about current issues, partner related temporary findings and process related content (eg: interviews); they will also help out mapping stakeholders with direct contact and with simple translations of content or double-checking on agencies' translations.

Attachment C: Short Project Presentation

PERCEIVE

Perception and Evaluation of
Regional and Cohesion Policies
by Europeans and Identification
with the Values of Europe

What

PERCEIVE is a three years research project part of Horizon 2020, the biggest Research and Innovation Programme of the EU. The project investigates, in different European regions, how much do citizens feel European and how do they perceive the implementation of the European Cohesion Policy.

Do European Citizens know what Cohesion Policy is and what does it do for them? How well does the European Union communicate its policies and positive results? Why do Europeans, in different regions, have a significantly different sense of belonging to the EU?

How

PERCEIVE will develop a comprehensive theory of “cohesion in diversity”, and use this theory to create a better understanding of the channels through which European policies contribute to create both different local understandings of the EU and different levels of European identification across profoundly different European regions.

Why

The research is expected to make major conceptual, methodological and analytical contribution towards a better understanding of the relationship between European regional policies, local and regional identities and the perception of the added value of the EU by its citizens.

These activities will inform communication strategies at the EU, Member State and regional levels regarding the European regional policies and specific projects. They will provide insights on how to adapt these communication efforts to local and regional realities in order to maximise their impact. At the same time, the research will consider how to increase the civic appreciation of these policies and how to improve regional policy relevance and efficiency.

Who

The countries involved are Italy, Sweden, Romania, Poland, Spain, United Kingdom, Austria, 9 partners from 8 European regions. Some of the most prestigious universities in Europe deploy their research groups to investigate on European Identity and share the research with European citizens:

- University of Bologna (Project Leader)
- University of Gothenburg
- Romanian Academy - Institute of Agricultural Economics
- Institute of Agricultural and Food Economics – National Research Institute
- University of Barcelona
- University of Portsmouth
- Vienna University of Economics and Business
- BAM! Strategie Culturali

When

Get in touch

Have something to say? Get in touch with us and join the conversation!

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www.perceiveproject.eu

Social Media

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/perceiveproject>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/PerceiveProject>

Newsletter

<http://www.perceiveproject.eu/get-in-touch>

Email

contact@perceiveproject.eu

Attachment C: Medium Project Presentation

PERCEIVE

Perception and Evaluation of
Regional and Cohesion Policies
by Europeans and Identification
with the Values of Europe

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- PERCEIVE project is led by University of Bologna
- Call: H2020-REFLECTIVE-SOCIETY-2015
- Topic: REFLECTIVE-3-2015: European cohesion, regional and urban policies and the perceptions of Europe
- Grant Agreement number: 693529
- Overall budget: €2.499.367,00
- Duration: 36 months starting from September 1 2016

PERCEIVE: Perception and Evaluation of Regional and Cohesion Policies by Europeans and Identification with the Values of Europe

Abstract

The PERCEIVE project aims at both mapping and explaining inter- and intra-regional variations in: the experiences and results of Cohesion Policy implementation; citizens' awareness and appreciation of EU efforts for delivering cohesion; and European identities and citizens' identification with the EU. In doing so, PERCEIVE will develop a comprehensive theory of "cohesion in diversity", and use this theory to create a better understanding of the channels through which European policies contribute to create both different local understandings of the EU and different levels of European identification across profoundly different European regions.

Challenge

Regional policies were the second largest part of the EU budget in the period of 2007-2013 and they will maintain a large budget share in the new Multiannual Financial Framework as well. The contribution of these policies towards European economic, social and territorial cohesion has been constantly monitored and critically analysed in recent years.

On the contrary, our knowledge is much less significant on the contribution of this vast European policy to a positive identification with the European project as such or to the emergence of a valued, popular sense of European identity among the beneficiary population.

Europe's regions are very diverse in terms of institutional history, distinct cultural (or even linguistic, ethnic or national) identities as well as administrative and governance functions. In some regions, indigenous peoples' issues and demands are affected and challenged by European policies. In the context of a perceived democratic deficit of the EU and bearing in mind the importance of local practices and mental representations in the construction of identities, it is highly important to analyse the triangular relationship between European regions, the European framework for the application of cohesion, regional and urban policies (including the notion of smart specialisation and the role of creativity in modern development policies) and the impact of European regional policies on a positive identification with the European construction.

Aim

The tailor-made, multidisciplinary, geographically balanced and comparative research of PERCEIVE will aim at exploring the interplay between:

- European regions with highly different administrative roles, civil participation, history, culture, creativity and identity;

- The application of cohesion, regional and urban policies in the EU, including the subsidiarity aspects and decentralised decision-making and the aims of smart specialisation;
- The contribution of regional policies to a positive identification with the value-based European integration project by European societies.

In analysing the potential of EU cohesion, regional and urban policies for fostering a more positive identification with the European project, it is also crucial to incorporate the interplay with regional policy regulatory implementation experiences, both positive and negative. Based on a critical review and assessment of the existing conceptual and methodological background supported by modern creative practice, the research should include a comparative analysis of genuine and innovative case studies from Member States with different current and historical territorial administrative frameworks and regional identities, in order to identify the channels by which European regional policies impact the perception of Europe by its citizens. Finally, the research activities should consider the impact and effectiveness of communication efforts related to EU-financed regional development projects.

Case Studies

The number of case study regions per country is closely linked to the level of information in terms of performance heterogeneity with which the regions contribute to the project objectives. Therefore, for two project partners' countries we selected two regions to better exploit their information power. This is the case of Italy, which displays very different development patterns among its regions that clearly follows a geographical North/South division and are able to influence the Cohesion Policy performance, and the case of Poland, where the Cohesion Policy performance is deeply influenced by a clear rural/urban division. In other project partners' countries, showing a lower degree of regional variation, we chose only one case study region. The countries and relative regions are:

Romania: Sud-Vest Oltenia

Poland: Dolnoslaskie, Warminsko-Mazurskie

Italy: Calabria, Emilia-Romagna

United Kingdom: Essex

Spain: Extremadura

Austria: Burgenland

Sweden: Norra Mellansverige

Theoretical Background

In addressing the aim of the project, PERCEIVE contrasts two different perspectives: a rational choice perspective stressing mainly the idea of institutions as "rules of the game" and the calculative rationality of actors as determinants of European identities and identification, and a social constructivist perspective stressing mainly the idea that European identities and identification emerge from a process of "social learning" associated with different institutional discourses.

PERCEIVE relies on a multidisciplinary portfolio of competences bridging socio-political, regional-economic and public administrative backgrounds. It integrates the use of both qualitative and quantitative analytical methods such as surveys, focus groups, case studies and econometric modelling. In addition, it uses particularly innovative methods such as quantitative discourse analysis to elicit meaning structures in public discourse about the EU, its regional policy and being European.

Finally, we will produce a computer simulation environment and embed it into a virtual platform that cohesion policy stakeholders will be able to use and to produce what-if analysis and long-term scenario analysis of the effects of policies.

Expected impact

The research is expected to make major conceptual, methodological and analytical contribution towards a better understanding of the relationship between European regional policies, local and regional identities and the perception of the added value of the EU by its citizens.

These activities will inform communication strategies at the EU, Member States and regional levels regarding the European regional policies and specific projects. They will provide insights on how to adapt these communication efforts to local and regional realities in order to maximise their impact. At the same time the research will consider how to increase the civic appreciation of these policies and how to improve regional policy relevance and efficiency.

Project Structure

PERCEIVE project is composed by nine different work packages:

WP1: Framework for comparative analysis: differences, implementation, perceptions and data gathering

WP2: Evaluation of EU citizens' perception of the EU project in relation to regional performance of the Cohesion Policy and institutional quality.

WP3: The effectiveness of projects' communication strategies

WP4: Spatial determinants of policy performance and synergies

WP5: The multiplicity of shared meanings of EU and Cohesion Regional and Urban Policy at different discursive levels.

WP6: Virtual learning environment

WP7: Dissemination and communication

WP8: Project Management

WP9: Ethic Requirements

The Consortium

PERCEIVE's partners have the perfect characteristics to take on the challenge of analysing a very complex interplay of regional diversities, policies' performance and citizens' perception of the European Union. These aspects will be investigated by taking both an economic and a sociological perspective. Hence, due to diverse backgrounds, excellent research and dissemination's skills, the final result of PERCEIVE will be a well-balanced project built on every partner's effort and contribution. An additional value to the project will be also brought by Local Managing Authorities, involved as third parties.

- University of Bologna (Project Leader)
- University of Gothenburg
- Romanian Academy - Institute of Agricultural Economics
- Institute of Agricultural and Food Economics – National Research Institute
- University of Barcelona
- University of Portsmouth
- Vienna University of Economics and Business
- BAM! Strategie Culturali

Contacts

Website

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Social Media

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<http://www.perceiveproject.eu/get-in-touch>

Email

contact@perceiveproject.eu